

CURRENT STATE OF PEDAGOGICAL PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR PUBLIC SPORTS AND HEALTH PROCESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077265>

Abstract: In this article, one of the main tasks of future pedagogues in modern society today is high professional competence and intellectual potential, loyalty, ideological conviction, and love for their profession. This distinguishes educators from other professions. Many programs on improving the quality and efficiency of education, forming their practical skills in subjects, and opinions on the priority tasks were expressed.

Key words and phrases: future pedagogues, new development, modern outlook, scientific-theoretical views, continuous education, individual qualities, well-rounded person, educational standards, civil society, scientific-methodology.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the continuous education system, one of the urgent tasks is to guide students to regular sports, to improve the system of preparation for health activities. In order to turn this process into a highly effective system, first of all, it is necessary to review the existing situation, study and identify its positive and negative aspects, fill in the shortcomings, abandon the old approaches, and at the same time improve the quality of education by using innovative methods. expected to be achieved.

Today, the acceleration and speed of the information exchange process complicates the upbringing of a mentally healthy generation. In the age of instant communication, the wide range of people's communication increases their mental stress. Intolerance, nervousness, and mental depression are observed among members of society. In such a situation, the task of improving the environment in every society, raising the future generation and personnel to be healthy both mentally and physically becomes urgent. Along with increasing the intellectual potential of young people, the tasks of developing their physical culture are emerging. That is why a number of activities are being carried out in our country to systematically organize the education of a healthy generation. In the speech delivered by the head of state Sh. Mirziyoyev at the ceremonial opening ceremony of the multi-disciplinary sports complex "Humo arena", he said: "Today we are implementing large-scale reforms and rapid changes in our

country. And in this way, bringing up a physically healthy and well-rounded generation is our priority, and we will mobilize all our strength and funds for this", it was a deep meaning and goal. Therefore, the preparation of general secondary education students for the process of sports rehabilitation is one of the activities for this purpose. Already, as a result of the special attention of the government to the field of physical education and sports, interest in the development of the process of sports health is increasing, physical education is becoming a daily activity. This, along with the development of a healthy lifestyle in society, is also preparing the ground for the rise of the sports industry in our country. After all, "establishing a healthy lifestyle in society, popularizing physical education and sports is an urgent task. From now on, we attach great importance to the rapid development of sports, the encouragement and support of athletes who have achieved high results in international competitions".[1] Therefore, within the framework of comprehensive work on the development of physical education and sports in our country, scientific research on the process of preparing students for the process of sports rehabilitation is also important. The second of the 5 important initiatives is aimed at directing young people to sports health activities, physical training, and creating conditions for them to practice physical education, sports, and self-expression. Over the past years, several works have been carried out in our republic, in addition to all regions, cities and districts, to develop sports, to create conditions for young people to engage in sports more widely, to create a healthy environment through physical education and health improvement in society. increased. The activities of sports clubs and schools were reorganized, mass sports competitions were held regularly.

METHODS

In improving the system of preparing students for the process of sports rehabilitation, first of all, a new approach to physical education, rehabilitation, physical maturity, physical development, strengthening of health, promotion of a healthy lifestyle is required. This research, carried out as part of the scientific justification of this necessity, serves as a scientific-theoretical source for improving the system of preparing students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation. Also, "under conditions of increasing global competition in all aspects of development, every country in the world needs to improve the quality of human capital today. This requires a fundamental revision of approaches to the issue of permanent care for the health of the nation - a healthy outlook, physical, spiritual and intellectual health of the population of all ages,

strengthening of physical health»[2]. "And in this way, it is our priority to bring up a physically healthy and well-rounded generation, and for this we must mobilize all our strength and resources."

In 2017, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the subject of physical education in the State Education Standard and the curriculum of general education schools. - 66 hours for classes, 68 hours for classes 2-3-4, 66-68 hours for classes 5-9, as well as elements of gymnastics, athletics, movement games, sports games: basketball, volleyball, handball , sports such as football and chess are set to be taught.[3]

The purpose of physical education classes is to make students healthy, develop physically, and educate them to become mature people in all respects. The tasks of physical education classes are to master the techniques and tactics of physical exercises and movements taught in this class. Therefore, even if the goal of each lesson does not change, the task of the lesson changes. In the course of physical education classes, not only the physical qualities of students are trained, but also their moral qualities of mutual cooperation, community, initiative, activity, bravery and fearlessness are trained. Also, in the course of physical education lessons, students should develop a sense of the Motherland and patriotic qualities.

It is appropriate to organize and conduct training taking into account the age, gender and physical fitness of students in preparing for mass sports health. Students acquire and improve the knowledge, skills and abilities provided for in the science program. In the main part of the lesson, according to the development of the lesson prepared by the teacher, new exercises specified in the physical education curriculum are taught in the classroom, or previously taught exercises are repeated, improved, and necessary theoretical knowledge is given. It is advisable to spend 25-30 minutes for the main part of physical education lessons. The organization of the main part of the lesson can be different. That is, the State educational standard for physical education requires the organization of sections of the curriculum (gymnastics, athletics, movement games, elements of sports games, chess) in the main part of the lesson using different methods.

RESULTS

Today, the attention to the formation of a healthy lifestyle culture among students is increasing. "The young generation is very susceptible to various influences. During this period of childhood, the conscious personal activity necessary for the formation of a healthy lifestyle is perfected. Promoting and

developing a healthy lifestyle among the population, strengthening population health and prolonging human life, prevention of infectious and other diseases, harmful habits, physical activity, proper nutrition and work, own Development of a number of measures aimed at timely rest, as well as observance of hygienic skills and its implementation in life is of great importance in the life of various groups of the population, especially students and young people".[4] Therefore, by directing students to the process of sports rehabilitation, it will be possible to improve their health and the social environment, thereby establishing a healthy lifestyle in society.

An important condition for preparing students for the process of sports rehabilitation is to make them engage in various sports and appreciate healthy life as a daily activity. Today, in preschool educational institutions, schools, lyceums and colleges of our country, the goal is to turn sports fitness activity into a national movement in the society, as well as to educate the next generation in a healthy way. The role of physical fitness activities is considered high in educating students as mature individuals both mentally and physically. Because a healthy body has intellectual abilities and potential.

One of the first stages of the mass sports rehabilitation process is the stages of pre-school and primary education. Today, there is wisdom in conducting physical education classes in educational institutions. Through this, it is aimed to develop the physical and health qualities of the young generation. In this case, the educational process shows that, on the one hand, it forms physical abilities in young people, and on the other hand, it is possible to educate them spiritually through physical influence. It also allows students to get basic physical education. In the pedagogical process, young people are given the opportunity to create a situation of conscious choice in order to become athletes in the future. With this, there is an opportunity to create the basis of physical potential necessary to become a mature person in all respects, a perfect person.

Studying the place of sports rehabilitation activities in the international education system in the development of innovative methods and improving the system of guiding students to the process of sports rehabilitation in the general secondary education system, its integration into the lifestyle of every person it should be noted that many scientific studies have been carried out on the analysis of its importance. As a result of the conducted scientific research, the system of physical education and sports health activities has its place in the world and in every country in it, and specific principles of physical education were developed. Those who follow these principles.

- the health principle of sports education;
- the principle of comprehensive, both spiritual and physical development of physical education.[5] So, it is known that mass sports health activities are based on physical education and development. Also, the tasks of improving the innovative foundations of physical education, introducing new approaches to it, and paying special attention to the formation of a healthy lifestyle culture in the educational environment are increasing.

DISCUSSION

Today, the goal is to prepare students for sports health activities, to form a culture of healthy lifestyle, and thereby improve their physical and mental health. However, there are many shortcomings in organizing this process and improving work efficiency. These include:

- the attitude of most school management towards physical education classes is not positive and physical education classes are not considered important lessons.
 - low capacity of teachers, lack of self-improvement or non-compliance with existing rules.
 - lack of equipment for organizing and conducting physical education classes.
 - the lack of excellent training in physical education for school education.
 - lack of special facilities for organizing and conducting physical education classes.
 - insufficient organization and discussion of open physical education classes.

In order to eliminate these shortcomings, we believe that the following actions should be carried out and we give them as a recommendation.

- achieving accurate and correct planning of physical education lessons (annual, quarterly, monthly);
 - to ensure the availability of facilities and equipment necessary for physical education classes;
 - observing the organization and conducting of physical education classes in 3 parts based on pedagogical requirements;
 - to achieve that the teacher can use the most effective methods of organizing students' activities in the lesson;
 - setting clear pedagogical tasks for physical education classes;
 - to follow the lesson by connecting the tasks of the previous lesson with the task of the next lesson;

Theoretical information on physical education is given in each physical education class in secondary schools, according to the subject of the lesson. During the lesson, as theoretical information, the techniques and tactics of performing physical exercises, the development of physical qualities, training in movement skills and abilities, and the prevention of injuries in physical education and sports are given. At the same time, in order to increase students' interest in physical education and sports, information is provided about the positive effects of physical exercises on the body, methods of using natural factors for health, and the lives of famous athletes.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, laws, presidential decrees, and decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers were adopted in the field of physical education and sports. The reforms carried out on the basis of the principles of social health of the society are aimed at forming a healthy social environment, well-rounded people, and a healthy culture of life in our country. This is done by strengthening people's health and improving their lifestyle. After all, ensuring public health is closely related to the state of the natural environment as well as the social environment. Therefore, striving to ensure the state of the social environment by protecting the biosocial health of a person is one of the important tasks of the state. In fact, if it is possible to have a positive effect on the gene pool of the nation by ensuring the physical health of the members of the society, it is possible to influence the whole society by directing the students to the process of sports health. can be shown.

The social goal of the system of training and directing students to the process of mass sports rehabilitation is to use their energy, enthusiasm and will in the economic, political and social changes taking place in our country. Therefore, by combining physical education and sports in education, it is aimed to increase the physical and mental potential of students and train personnel who meet world standards. After all, "today, modern and convenient sports infrastructure is being built in all regions of our country, even in the most remote districts. In the next two years, the number of people who regularly do sports in our country doubled".[6] This is also one of the important stages in improving the process of improving the health of sports through physical education and sports in our country.

Mass sports health activities develop the personality of students and improve their stature. Also, morphological and functional changes occur in students, body structure, weight, muscle strength, lung capacity, chest excursion have high indicators, mental, moral qualities is brought up. In this regard, the

importance of the sports rehabilitation process is high. In this sense, it is necessary to pay special attention to physical training and sports[7]. Therefore, the process of mass sports rehabilitation is a pedagogical process aimed at the physical development of students, and it is aimed at the development of movement skills and abilities and average physical qualities. Mental, moral, aesthetic and labor training is carried out simultaneously in activities aimed at sports rehabilitation. Therefore, "physical maturity is characterized by complete health, a person's long-term active life and a number of other indicators - comprehensive and high-level manifestation of physical and mental ability to work in any external environment, physical and volitional qualities, It means that it consists of harmonious development of large-scale movement skills and body shape.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be concluded that the current state of preparation of students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation in practice is not very exemplary, and the practice of physical education and healthy lifestyle formation is not at the required level. On the basis of today's social demand, there is a need to improve the system of preparing students for mass sports rehabilitation.

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